

SEXUAL INEQUALITY IN HEMP

Male Plants Die While Females Grow Vigorously Under Same Conditions—
Possible Sex-Limited Environmental Character Suggested—Advantage to
Females of Death of Males—Reversal of Usual Effects of Selection.

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A STRIKING example of sexual inequality was noticed in August, 1912, in a plot of hemp that was being grown on the Virginia Truck Experiment Station, near Norfolk. The nature of the inequality will be apparent by reference to figures 9 and 10. All of the male plants were very slender and spindling, and the foliage was of a pale yellowish green color, in strong contrast with the deep blackish green of the female plants. In addition to their more robust form, the female plants were often a foot taller than adjacent males, the largest of the female plants attaining about three feet. Many of the male plants had already died at the time the photographs were taken, August 13, and the others were evidently to follow shortly. But all of the female plants were still fresh and vigorous, and were growing and flowering under conditions that were bringing the male plants to an early death.

To describe the female plants as stronger and more resistant than the male plants seems a rather inadequate statement of so great an inequality of behavior. If two species were tested and were found to react so differently we would say that one of them was adapted to the conditions, and that some essential character was lacking in the other. With two sexes of the same plant behaving so differently, the idea of a sex-limited environmental character is suggested. Certainly there is no general reason or analogy for believing that sex alone would explain so great a difference of behavior under the same conditions.

In the perennial plants that have the sexes represented by separate individuals, as among the dates, figs, carobs, poplars, rubber trees, etc., the male individuals appear to have greater vigor and longevity than the females. No doubt it would be an advantage in an annual plant like the hemp to have the males die out after they have shed their pollen. The early death of the males means less competition with the adjacent female plants while these are engaged in maturing seed. The more unfavorable the conditions the more desirable that the males die early in order to increase the chances that the seed be matured. But the advantage of having the males die earlier would not of itself cause them to die. Some other specialization or intensification of the sexual differences must have arisen. On account of the factor of competition between the sexes the usual effects of selection would be reversed. Under extreme conditions short-lived male plants would be likely to leave larger progenies than long-lived males, for the female plants that stood next to short-lived males would be able to ripen more seed. The natural result of such variation and selection would be the development of a plant with short-lived, ephemeral males corresponding to drone bees and similar specializations of the sexes among insects and other invertebrate animals.

WHY THE PLANTS DIE.

It would be interesting to determine the extent to which the presence or the competition of the female plants may be responsible for the early death of the male plants. This could be learned by

FEMALE AND MALE HEMP PLANTS.

The three females (at the left) are growing vigorously, while the three males (at the right), under identical conditions, are dying or already dead. The difference in behavior is so extreme that Mr. Cook suggests a possible sex-limited environmental character to account for it, since it seems improbable that sex alone would explain so great a difference of behavior under the same conditions. (Figure 9.)

SEXUAL INEQUALITY IN A FIELD OF HEMP.

Plants of a Chinese form of hemp, grown at Norfolk, Virginia, and photographed in August, 1912. All of the leafy plants that are readily seen are females, the very slender, thread-like stems representing the males. It seems to be an advantage to the species (this being an annual) to have the males die as soon as they have yielded their pollen, for their competition is thus removed and the females given a better chance to produce seed. Mr. Cook suggests that a reversal of the usual effects of selection would develop a race of plants with short-lived, ephemeral males corresponding to drone bees. (Figure 10.)

raising some of the male plants in plots by themselves. If male plants were found to live longer alone than with the female plants, it might be inferred that they are starved or strangled by the female plants, just as the dwarf male spiders are often killed and eaten by their huge and hungry mates. In both cases the death of the males contributes incidentally to the welfare of the progeny, whereas their continued existence would not.

OTHER VARIETIES LESS UNEQUAL

In the ordinary varieties of hemp grown for fibre or drug purposes there is no such striking inequality of the sexes. Though the male plants die somewhat in advance of the females, they attain nearly the same stature and live through most of the season. The variety that shows this extreme inequality of the sexes is recognized by L. H. Dewey as the so-called Russian or Manchurian hemp, which is extensively grown in Europe and Asia, not for the fibre, but for seed. The oil extracted from the seed is used for food and also has rapid-drying qualities that render it of interest to manufacturers of paint and varnish. The plant has not been grown on a commercial scale in the United States, but attention is now being given to this possibility. The seed crop is much larger than with the varieties grown for fibre, for which the earlier mortality of the males may be partly responsible. Indeed, if the sexes had an equal development it would be hard to believe that a dioecious plant could compete with a bisexual species in seed production. This may be a reason why there are relatively few dioecious plants among annuals.

With perennial plants there could be no corresponding advantage in having the males short-lived. The existence of perennials is not so acutely dependent upon the production of seed every year as upon the ability to gain and hold ground against the competition of other species. In this struggle, large, long-lived male plants doubtless have advantages that more than counterbalance the factor of competition between the sexes. But even with perennials the general tendency of selection is probably in favor of the bisexual types and against the separation of the sexes in different individuals.

SHORTENING OF INTERNODES.

Another peculiarity of the oil-seed hemp is that the lateral fruit-bearing branches have extremely short internodes, analogous to those of the so-called cluster varieties of cotton. The shortening of the fruiting branches may also be connected with the earliness and productiveness of the crop, from which high yields of seed are obtained. This form of hemp, according to Mr. Dewey, is probably the same as that described by Pallas as *Cannabis erratica*, though it is not usually considered as a species distinct from the ordinary *Cannabis sativa*. It has probably been cultivated in China since a very remote period. References to the sexual diversification of the hemp plant in Chinese literature are dated as far back as 2700 B. C.

NOTE.—The Editor has called my attention to a paper that is to be published in the same issue of the Journal, in which a theory of sex-determination appears to have been based largely on experiments with hemp. The inequality of the sexes naturally suggests the question whether the results ascribed to sex determination might not be due to other causes, such as unequal susceptibility of the seedlings to adverse environmental conditions.

Lectures Are In Demand

Announcement in a recent issue of the JOURNAL OF HEREDITY that a lecturer was now available for talks on eugenics, has led to a gratifying demand for the services of A. Edward Hamilton, of the Eugenics Record Office, Cold Spring Harbor, Long Island, New York. He can be secured by clubs, colleges and other organizations which wish to give serious attention to eugenics; his services are made available through the liberality of Mrs. Huntington Wilson, of this association.